

Supplementary table 1. Oligonucleotides used in real-time PCR assays

Gene	Forward sequence	Reverse sequence
mKi67	5'-AGAGCTAACTTGCGCTGACT-3'	5'-TCAATACTCCTTCCAAACAGGCA-3'
mCdk1	5'-ACACGAGGTAGTGACGCTGT-3'	5'-TCAATCTCTGAGTCGCCGTG-3'
mCcnB2	5'-CCGACGGTGTCCAGTGATTT-3'	5'-CTGAGGTTTCTTCGCCACCT-3'
mArg1	5'-GAATCTGCATGGGCAACCT-3'	5'-ACACGATGTCTTTGGCAGATAT-3'
mFizz1	5'-GGAAGTTCTTGCCAATCCAGC-3'	5'-AAGCCACAAGCACACCCAGT-3'
mYm1	5'-GAAGGAGCCACTGAGGTCTG-3'	5'-GAGCCACTGAGCCTTCAAC-3'
mMrc1	5'-TTCAGCTATTGGACGCGAGG-3'	5'-GAATCTGACACCCAGCGGAA-3'
mVegfa	5'-AGCAGAAGTCCCATGAAGTGA-3'	5'-ATGTCCACCAGGGTCTCAAT-3'
rKi67	5'-CCACAACCAGGAAGACCAGTT-3'	5'-TGATCCCATTATCCGCCTGC-3'
rCdk1	5'-GGGAACAGAGAGGGTCCGTT-3'	5'-ATTTCCCGGATTGCCGTACT-3'
rArg1	5'-ACAAGACAGGGCTACTTTCAGG-3'	5'-ACAAGACAAGGTCAACGCCA-3'
rMrc1	5'-CAACTCTTGGACTIONCACGGCA-3'	5'-ATGATCTGCGACTCCGACAC-3'
mIL-4Ra	5'-AACTCGCAGGTTCTGGCTGG-3'	5'-AAGCCCCGAGTCCTAGGTT-3'
36B4	5'-GGCGACCTGGAAGTCCAAC-3'	5'-CCATCAGCACCACGGCCTTC-3'

m = mouse; r = rat